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A scalable matching approach for the comparison of agricultural land use maps based on corresponding field polygons

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ABSTRACT

Establishing sustainable agricultural systems while ensuring food security has become a global priority. Meeting this goal requires contributions from different fields of agricultural science, many of which depend on detailed information on crops. Recent advancements in deep learning and the transnational harmonization of administrative data have led to the availability of ever-larger datasets of agricultural field polygons. These datasets, however, vary in quality and level of detail. To achieve synergies between different information sources through data fusion and to evaluate the quality of model outputs, it is essential to efficiently identify correspondences in spatially overlapping datasets. We address this challenge by leveraging a state-of-the-art matching algorithm that we adapt by redesigning its connected-component decomposition to handle large-scale datasets of agricultural field polygons. We demonstrate the algorithm's suitability through two case studies. First, we show how automatically delineated field polygons can be validated against ground truth in terms of their spatial quality. Second, we explore how two established reference datasets align both thematically and spatially. We discuss the dataset comparisons using different evaluation metrics and provide an interactive map viewer that enables the exploration of spatial patterns of the datasets' alignment by visualizing matching qualities in the geographic context.

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1. Introduction

Ensuring the long-term sustainability of agricultural systems is increasingly important in the light of climate change and growing populations. To address this challenge, it is essential to have a comprehensive understanding of where, when, and what is or has been cultivated in the fields (Hadeed et al. 2024). In this context, applications such as agricultural monitoring, yield forecasting, or the assessment of environmental policy impacts rely on information on field polygons of crops (Sagris, Kikas, and Angileri 2015; Nakalembe and Kerner 2023). Although such data were long limited in scope and availability, recent years have seen major progress, particularly through the harmonisation of administrative records and the automated delineation of field polygons from satellite imagery (Kerner et al. 2025). Large datasets from different sources covering the same regions have become available, differing in their spatial and semantic quality and granularity.

This premise presents two primary motivations for data comparison: one is to integrate or fuse datasets to combine complementary information; the other is to validate automatically generated data against a ground truth. In both cases, a key requirement is the identification of correspondences between the spatial entities of the datasets involved, see for example Figure 1.

Figure 1. Correspondences (matches) between two sets of agricultural land use polygons. Dashed outlines represent polygons delineated using machine learning, while solid fills indicate polygons from administrative information. Colours indicate different matches, while polygons without correspondences are shown in grey. *Background imagery by Google (2025).*

Figure 2. Different types of matching multiplicities between two datasets. Shown are real-world instances from land use data of Germany's official topographic database (blue) and the *Integrated Administration and Control System* of the European Union (orange).

However, finding these correspondences is not trivial since they are not necessarily limited to one-to-one relationships. In fact, three types of relations may occur: one-to-one (1:1), one-to-many (1:n), and many-to-many ($m:n$) (see Figure 2).

Specifically, when it comes to the validation of large datasets of automatically delineated field polygons, established approaches typically build geometric correspondences by either considering only 1:1 correspondences (Zhu et al. 2024), applying local ad-hoc assignments (Van Coillie et al. 2010; Radoux and Bogaert 2017), or analysing sampled subsets of the data (Congalton and Green 2008). These methods are limited in their ability to detect complex $m:n$ correspondences, do not clearly define global mathematical objectives, or may fail to capture local anomalies or spatial inhomogeneities within specific areas of agricultural land use. Consequently, quality issues may remain undetected, particularly when they occur in localised regions or follow patterns that do not substantially affect commonly used overall accuracy measures.

Thus, we argue that there is a lack of tools and frameworks that support the efficient and scalable global comparison of entire datasets in a many-to-many fashion. This aligns with recent calls in the literature for more advanced accuracy assessment tools and improved strategies for integrating large land use datasets (Zhang and Li 2022).

Addressing these needs, we leverage the scalable matching algorithm introduced by Naumann, Bonerath, and Haurert (2025) that was originally developed for comparing building footprints. By redesigning its decomposition of connected components, we adapt this algorithm for the identification of correspondences between large-scale datasets of agricultural land use polygons.

By spatially matching polygons across datasets, it enables a thorough evaluation of spatial completeness and consistency, while also helping to identify semantic discrepancies in crop type assignments. Moreover, the establishment of correspondences allows for the integration of attribute information across sources.

To demonstrate the algorithm's versatility and to highlight its utility for a scalable quality assessment in the agricultural domain, we present two comprehensive case studies. First, we qualitatively assess a recently published, Europe-wide dataset of field polygons that has been automatically delineated from Sentinel-2 satellite imagery (Batiç 2024). To evaluate its spatial completeness and quality, we compare it against official administrative data on crop fields reported by farmers through the EU's *Integrated Administration and Control System* (IACS). Specifically, we conduct this comparison across five different countries, which involves matching datasets of up to 10 million polygons.

While the use of IACS data as a reference is widespread, it is also recognised that perfect ground truth is often implicitly assumed, yet rarely exists in practice (Foody 2024). To address this, we conduct a second case study in which we compare two commonly used reference sources of field polygons to assess both their thematic and spatial consistency. Specifically, we compare IACS data with agricultural land use polygons from Germany's official topographic database (*Amtliches Topographisch-Kartographisches Informationssystem, ATKIS*).

With regard to the matching-based dataset comparisons in both case studies, we provide comprehensive evaluations considering different quality and consistency aspects. In particular, we assess and discuss

- the alignment of datasets based on the distribution of matched and unmatched polygons,
- the spatial quality of identified matches using different geometric measures,
- the granularity across datasets by analysing the match multiplicities,
- the semantic consistency across matched field polygons, and
- spatial congruency discrepancies across different thematic classes.

Beyond these thorough assessments, we provide a web-based visualisation tool that allows users to visually explore different comparison metrics across the datasets. Implemented as an interactive map viewer, it offers visualisations designed to effectively communicate the data's spatial and semantic alignment in a geographically contextualised manner. For a look and feel of the tool, a demo is available that showcases the case studies presented in this article¹.

In summary, the scientific contributions of this article are as follows:

- We adapt an efficient matching algorithm and demonstrate its suitability for large-scale datasets of agricultural field polygons.
- We provide an open-source implementation of the algorithm in C++ to support reproducibility and further development.
- We present two case studies showcasing the versatility and applicability of the algorithm across different scenarios for field polygon comparisons.
- We share a web-based visualisation tool that allows users to intuitively explore key comparison metrics within the data's geographical context.

2. Related work

Monitoring agricultural land use has become a critical task in recent years, driven by the growing need for informed decision-making in global food production (Tantalaki, Souravlas, and Roumeliotis 2019). Establishing sustainable agricultural systems while ensuring food security has become a global objective (Shahmohammadloo et al. 2021), reflected in the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations 2015). In the context of climate change and growing populations, the conservation of biodiversity, increased land demand, the management of economic and political pressures, and the maintenance of soil

health represent major challenges in achieving this objective (Farooq, Rehman, and Pisante 2019; Mamabolo, Makwela, and Tsilo 2020; MacPherson et al. 2022). To support effective policymaking and environmental action, a wide range of agricultural sciences rely on the availability of data on land use and crop dynamics (Sagris, Kikas, and Angileri 2015; Nakalembe and Kerner 2023). Agricultural land use is typically represented through geospatially referenced information on crops in the form of field polygons, sometimes referred to as *crop maps* (Upcott et al. 2023; Wang et al. 2024).

In the following, we provide an overview of scientific work on the automatic delineation of field boundaries and polygons, with a particular focus on the quality assessment of such automatically generated data. In this context, we highlight the importance of establishing correspondences between delineated and reference polygons and therefore discuss current algorithmic approaches for polygon matching.

2.1. Automatic field polygon delineation

Traditionally, information on field polygons is based on cadastral data, established through on-site surveying techniques (Sagris, Kikas, and Angileri 2015; Masoud, Persello, and Tolpekin 2019). Given that this kind of data collection is extremely time-consuming and labour-intensive, research in the era of Agriculture 4.0 (Araújo et al. 2021) is increasingly focusing on the automatic delineation of agricultural field polygons (Masoud, Persello, and Tolpekin 2019; Persello et al. 2019; Mei et al. 2022; Jeon, Kim, and Kim 2025). The availability of high-resolution satellite imagery, combined with the advances in deep learning technologies, has led to new possibilities for extracting land use information directly from remote sensing data (Vali, Comai, and Matteucci 2020; Wang, Waldner, and Lobell 2022). Established approaches rely on object-based image analysis (Blaschke 2010), where coherent agricultural fields are identified through segmentation algorithms. For a comprehensive overview of scientific studies using deep learning strategies for field polygon delineation, we refer to the recent review by Xu et al. (2024).

When applying segmentation strategies for the automatic delineation of field polygons, one key concern is the quality of the results. In this context, supervised evaluation methods are typically employed which compare a model's output to a reference dataset (Costa, Foody, and Boyd 2018). Most commonly, thematic accuracy metrics are derived from the *confusion matrix*, also known as *error matrix* (Stehman 1997). These include measures such as *overall accuracy*, *precision*, and *recall* which quantify how well a thematic classification corresponds to the ground truth at a pixel level. While such pixel-based metrics are well suited for general classification outputs, they are less appropriate for evaluating field polygons on an object level (Ye, Pontius, and Rakshit 2018). In this context, North, Pairman, and Belliss (2018) argue that '*agricultural land use statistics are more informative per-field than per-pixel.*' Similarly, Congalton and Green (2008) emphasise that '*if the map to be assessed is a polygon map, then the accuracy assessment sample units should also be polygons.*'

Addressing this issue, an object-based accuracy assessment considers the geometric alignment of output and reference objects (Blaschke 2010). This strategy enables the evaluation not only of thematic but also geometric accuracy, making it particularly suitable for assessing delineated field polygons (Möller et al. 2013; Zhu et al. 2024). Most commonly, geometric accuracy metrics rely on the overlap between delineated and reference polygons—such as the *Intersection over Union (IoU)*, also known as the *Jaccard Index*. These metrics are particularly well suited for detecting over- or under-segmentation, where a delineated polygon is either smaller or larger than the corresponding reference polygon, respectively (Möller, Lymburner, and Volk 2007). For a comprehensive overview of established geometric metrics, we refer to the reviews of Costa, Foody, and Boyd (2018) and Jozdani and Chen (2020).

In general, applying object-based evaluation metrics requires the establishment of correspondences between the delineated and reference polygons. Three types of relations may arise: one-to-one, one-to-many, and many-to-many (Costa, Foody, and Boyd 2018). To identify such correspondences, common strategies range from manually matching the data (North, Pairman, and Belliss 2018), comparing object identifiers (Möller et al. 2013), or applying a basic geometry-based matching (Conrad et al. 2010; Li et al. 2016; Pahmeyer, Kuhn, and Storm 2025). The latter typically involves applying a threshold that defines a minimum percentage of spatial overlap between delineated and reference polygons.

However, the specific methods used are often not described in detail, and a standardised approach for matching delineated polygons with reference polygons has yet to be established (Ye, Pontius, and Rakshit

2018). Furthermore, not least because of the complexity involved in establishing accurate correspondences, object-based evaluations are typically not conducted on the entire dataset (Radoux and Bogaert 2017). Instead, sampling strategies are employed to select a representative subset of objects for which both thematic and geometric accuracy are assessed. Choosing an effective sampling strategy remains one of the most challenging and critical tasks in the accuracy assessment (Congalton and Green 2008).

In this article, we propose an efficient and scalable method that enables a comprehensive geometric matching of large field polygon datasets. This approach allows for determining correspondences between delineated and reference polygons across the entire dataset, thereby facilitating an object-based accuracy evaluation at scale.

2.2. State-of-the-art polygon matching

Regarding the theoretical foundation of polygon matching methods, extensive work has been done in the field of building footprint matching. Generally, three main types of approaches have been studied: heuristics, machine-learning methods, and optimisation methods. The key commonality of the introduced heuristic approaches (Hecht, Kunze, and Hahmann 2013; Fan et al. 2014; Müller, Iosifescu, and Hurni 2015; Chen et al. 2024) is that they do not state a problem definition. This makes the algorithms less clearly outlined and their results less globally classifiable, which is why we do not use a heuristic algorithm in this article. Machine learning approaches range from support vector machines (Xu et al. 2024) to back-propagation neural networks (Zhu et al. 2021) and deep autoencoder networks (Xu et al. 2017). All of these methods require (large) labelled training datasets, which is a major bottleneck, as it takes a lot of time for experts to create such data. Moreover, the training data can contain biases specific to patterns unique to the covered region. This leads to a reduced transferability when the algorithm is applied to data that has a different structure. A machine learning algorithm trained with expert data mimics the expert's behaviour, which can be an important task. However, in our use case, we need clearly defined and objective matchings to automatically evaluate or integrate multiple datasets. Furthermore, it should transfer well to data of different characteristics, as it will be applied to large-scale field polygons from different countries and sources. This is why we use the optimisation algorithm introduced by Naumann, Bonerath, and Haunert (2025) to compute matchings. It is based on a global problem definition and maximises the sum of all single match scores in a matching. It has been shown to scale well on large building footprint datasets, which is why we include it as our core algorithm for finding spatial correspondences between two datasets of agricultural land use polygons.

3. Available datasets and ground truth sources

As discussed in Section 2.1, recent years have seen a growing research focus on the automatic delineation of crop field polygons. While many studies focus on developing and evaluating novel deep learning methodologies, there are only a few publicly available datasets containing actual model-generated field polygons. Among the notable contributions is the *UKFields* dataset (Bancroft and Wilkins 2024), published as part of the *Field Boundaries of Agriculture* (FIBOA) initiative. This dataset provides automatically delineated fields across England, Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland. Expanding the geographic scope to a continental scale, the *Open Earth Monitor Cyberinfrastructure* (OEMC) project recently released a dataset comprising over 51 million field polygons across Europe (Batiç 2024).

A prerequisite for the quality of such datasets is the availability of labelled data to serve as ground truth for both training and evaluation of the models used (Burke et al. 2021). To support this need, scientific studies have focused on creating and publishing comprehensive benchmark datasets. However, many of these datasets are geographically constrained, often limited to specific countries or small regions. For example, the *PASTIS* dataset (Garnot and Landrieu 2021) focuses on France, *Sen4AgriNet* (Sykas et al. 2022) extends this coverage to include Catalonia, and *AI4SmallFarms* (Persello et al. 2023) encompasses areas in Vietnam and Cambodia. To enable a more robust benchmarking across a wider range of landscapes and latitudes, continent-wide datasets such as *AI4Boundaries* (d'Andrimont et al. 2023) for Europe and a dataset by Wussah et al. (2024) for Africa have been provided. Improving the spatial coverage even further, recent projects like *GloCAB* (Hall, Argueta, and Giglio 2024) and *Fields of the*

World (Kerner et al. 2025) offer globally distributed training datasets for field polygon segmentation in the agricultural domain.

Most of these benchmark datasets use administrative information on agricultural land use as ground truth. In the European Union, such data is collected to administer agricultural subsidies under the *Common Agricultural Policy* (CAP) - the EU's primary framework for supporting agriculture (European Commission 2018). To manage CAP payments, the *Integrated Administration and Control System* (IACS) functions as the overarching mechanism for monitoring compliance and distributing the subsidies (Leonhardt et al. 2024). Within IACS, the two main geospatial components are the *Land Parcel Identification System* (LPIS), which provides reference parcels for aid applications, and the *Geospatial Aid Application* (GSAA), which allows farmers to digitally declare the location and extent of their agricultural activities. The LPIS reference parcels store general land use information—such as arable land, permanent crops, or permanent grassland—while GSAA contains the annually self-declared crop types within these parcels (Toth and Milenov 2020).

Since a reform in 2021, EU Member States participating in the CAP have been required to make the annually collected land use data publicly accessible. This reform marked an essential step toward implementing the FAIR data principles for data reuse of Wilkinson et al. (2016) and provided a major boost for progress across the various fields of agricultural science (Leonhardt et al. 2024). However, as the data is published individually by each Member State (or even by regional authorities), it is scattered across national databases and often uses different formats and standards. This fragmentation makes it cumbersome to access the data for research purposes (Sagris, Kikas, and Angileri 2015). Addressing this issue, the *EuroCrops* project (Schneider et al. 2023) gathers and harmonises IACS land use information from across the EU Member States. It provides a unified, large-scale dataset of field polygons along with the information on the crop species cultivated in each field.

In this article, we evaluate the dataset of Batiç (2024) as a recent publication of automatically delineated field polygons, by examining its alignment with official IACS polygons collected within the *EuroCrops* project (Schneider et al. 2023). Furthermore, we investigate the consistency of the IACS data with another widely used ground truth source, the German official topographic database *ATKIS*, as exemplarily shown in Figure 2.

4. Methodology

To describe the algorithm that we use to find spatial correspondences between two datasets of field polygons, we first need to introduce the necessary terminology. Generally, a matching M of two sets of polygons L_1 and L_2 is defined as a set of matches μ . Every match μ consists of two sets of polygons $P \subseteq L_1$ and $Q \subseteq L_2$. Both of these sets can have an arbitrary size. This leads to different kinds of match multiplicities that can occur, see Figure 2. If single entities of the two input datasets align well, they get assigned as 1:1 (one-to-one) matches. However, if the two datasets contain differing polygon representations for the same area, it becomes necessary to allow for 1: n (one-to-many) or even m : n (many-to-many) matches. If there is no corresponding counterpart to a polygon of one input dataset, it can be assigned as a 1:0 (or 0:1) match. We will refer to such polygons as being unmatched.

To compute said matching, we utilise the algorithm introduced by Naumann, Bonerath, and Haunert (2025). In the following paragraph, we provide a short description of the algorithm. For further details, we refer to their work.

As input, the algorithm expects the two sets of (land use) polygons L_1 and L_2 , see Figure 3(a). It first computes a hierarchical grouping for each of these datasets, see Figure 3(b).

These hierarchies can be understood as tree graphs T_1 and T_2 , i.e. connected graphs with no cycles. Every vertex in these trees represents a set of polygons. One can now form a third graph G containing all vertices from both trees T_1 and T_2 , as shown in Figure 3(c). Edges $e = \{u \in T_1, v \in T_2\}$ can be inserted connecting vertices from both trees. Every edge is assigned a weight $w(e)$ that describes how well the represented sets of polygons align with each other. The task of matching the two datasets can be formulated as selecting a subset of edges in G that maximises the total weight, subject to the constraint that along any path from the root to a leaf in either tree, at most one vertex is matched. This constraint is crucial, as it ensures that no

Figure 3. Example of the algorithm's hierarchical grouping.

polygons is matched more than once. The problem is known as the *tree-constrained bipartite matching problem*. To solve it, we apply the approximation algorithm proposed by Canzar et al. (2011). Naturally, it is of core importance how to choose the weights of the edges in G as this determines the outcome of the matching. The algorithm of Canzar et al. (2011) allows for an arbitrary choice of the weights. In their work, Naumann, Bonerath, and Haurert (2025) use a measure based on the Intersection over Union (IoU) to evaluate the quality of a match. This geometric measure is established and has been shown to perform well in practice (Jozdani and Chen 2020). For this reason, we adopt the same approach and define the edge weight as $w(e = (u, v)) = \text{IoU}(p(u), p(v)) - \lambda$, where $p(v)$ is the set of polygons represented by a vertex $v \in V(G)$. The additional parameter $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ acts as a threshold, discarding matches with an IoU below λ . Its value is manually set during the experiments. Altogether, this leads to the algorithm finding a matching that fulfills the tree-constraints and (approximately) maximises

$$\sigma(M) = \sum_{\mu \in M} (\text{IoU}(\mu) - \lambda). \quad (1)$$

Intuitively, we are thereby looking for a matching that, in sum over all matches, has the maximum quality. This implies that we generally favour finding more matches, as this leads to more elements in our sum, which is intended, as more matches imply more precise matches (smaller m and n in $m:n$ matches). Larger many-to-many matches only occur if they cannot be split into smaller matches that in sum exceed their quality. As proven by Naumann, Bonerath, and Haurert (2024), choosing this objective ensures that there is always an optimal solution containing only *connected* matches. To introduce connectedness, we make use of an intersection graph G_{int} . This graph contains a vertex per polygon in both input datasets L_1 and L_2 . An edge $e = (u \in L_1, v \in L_2)$ exists if and only if the corresponding polygons intersect. Using this structure, a match μ is connected if and only if the subgraph of G_{int} induced by all of the vertices representing the polygons in μ is connected. This property enables the use of a decomposition technique: As there is an optimal solution consisting of connected matches only, we can decompose the input into connected components of G_{int} and solve them individually. This allows for parallelisation and substantially reduces the size of the individual problems to be solved. An overview of the algorithm used to compute matchings is outlined in Algorithm 1.

As stated above, the algorithm computes a many-to-many matching between the two input datasets. By our choice of the objective function, it implicitly also assigns every match a quality ($\text{IoU} - \lambda$) that can be used for analysis and visualisation. However, this measure is not a limitation: once the correspondences are established, any quality metric can be applied to assess the identified correspondences. In our case studies,

Algorithm 1. POLYGON_MATCHING

Input: Sets of polygons L_1, L_2
Output: Matching M of L_1 and L_2

- 1: $M \leftarrow \emptyset$
- 2: $C \leftarrow$ connected components of G_{int} of L_1 and L_2
- 3: **foreach** component $c = (C_1 \subseteq L_1, C_2 \subseteq L_2) \in C$ **do**
- 4: $T_1, T_2 \leftarrow \text{BUILD_TREES}(C_1, C_2)$
- 5: $M_c \leftarrow \text{TREE_CONSTRAINED_MATCHING}(T_1, T_2)$
- 6: $M \leftarrow M \cup M_c$
- 7: **end for**
- 8: **return** M

we leverage this flexibility and analyse the matchings also using a different geometric metric proposed in the literature.

Adaptation for Agricultural Land Use Polygons. To improve the applicability of the algorithm to our specific scenario of matching field polygons, we extended the implementation provided by Naumann, Bonerath, and Haurert (2025). Most importantly, we changed the logic regarding the decomposition into connected components: The baseline code computes the pointwise union of both datasets to form a third set of polygons. It then determines, for each polygon in this union, which polygons from the input datasets lie within it. This approach works well for the algorithm’s original domain of building footprints, which generally have simple, mostly rectangular geometries and are often freestanding. Land use polygons, however, tend to be more complex and directly adjacent to one another. In such cases, this strategy becomes less effective and more prone to numerical instabilities. Using the union of all input polygons can produce subgroups that contain multiple connected components in the intersection graph, particularly when many polygons share boundaries. We therefore added the functionality of precomputing the connected components by constructing the intersection graph G_{int} and decomposing it, see Figure 4. We modified the existing implementation to take these components as input. This speeds up the matching process and circumvents numerical issues, while reducing memory load. Moreover, we extended the code with functionalities for visualising the matching qualities and results. This enhancement makes the matching results, and especially their evaluation process, accessible to users interested in assessing datasets beyond those considered in this article. The code used in this work is available in an online repository².

Running Time and Memory Complexity. In this paragraph, we provide a brief description of the theoretical bounds of Algorithm 1 with respect to both running time and memory. These bounds represent the behaviour of the algorithm in the worst case. An exemplary worst-case instance would be an input pair of large sets of polygons, where every polygon of one set intersects every polygon of the other set. Due to the local limitation of the extent of land use polygons and the general structure of the geographical objects, such configuration is highly unlikely in practice. For real-world datasets, the algorithm’s running time and memory consumption will therefore remain substantially below the theoretical worst-case bounds. Nevertheless, we include the following analysis for the sake of methodological completeness. Let N be the total number of input polygons and M be the total number of edges of these polygons. In our case of matching polygons representing geographical objects, it is reasonable to assume that the polygons cannot be arbitrarily complex. This means that there is a constant c_M upper-bounding the maximum number of edges in a single polygon across both input datasets. Hence, N depends linearly on M , as $N \leq c_M M$. We will therefore base our analysis on N as an indicator of the input size. To reduce the computation effort necessary for the geometric computations included in lines 4 and 5 of Algorithm 1, we precompute a line arrangement per component c . This allows us to compute the areas per face of the arrangement once, determine which face is part of which input polygon, and store this information. It can be utilised for constant-time look-ups when computing intersections and unions. Furthermore, we will treat the subroutine TREE_CONSTRAINED_MATCHING proposed by Canzar et al. (2011) as a black box that runs in polynomial time, as exact bounds depend on the algorithm used to solve the underlying linear programs.

Figure 4. Example of the structure of the intersection graph G_{int} that we decompose into connected components.

Such an analysis is beyond the scope of our contribution. We will refer to $R_T(x)$ and $M_T(x)$ as its running time and memory consumption, respectively, depending on the number x of vertices in the input trees. Regarding the overall running time of Algorithm 1, the initial decomposition of input polygons into connected components lies in $O(N^2)$. In the worst case, the entire dataset describes one component of size N . The BUILD_TREES subroutine also takes $O(N^2)$ time, as shown by Naumann, Bonerath, and Haunert (2025). As the trees are binary, their number of vertices is linear in N . This leads to an overall worst-case running time complexity of $O(N^2 + R_T(N))$ the memory requirement of finding the connected components is in $O(N)$. The line arrangement, which in the worst case includes all N input polygons as one single component, needs $O(N^2)$ memory. Therefore, we have a total memory complexity of $O(N^2 + M_T(N))$. However, in practice, the datasets decompose into many smaller components, reducing both running time and memory requirements substantially.

5. Experimental evaluation

Our experimental evaluation comprises two comprehensive case studies. The first assesses automatically delineated field polygons against reference data, while the second compares two authoritative datasets to evaluate their thematic and geometric consistency. For all our experiments, we applied Algorithm 1 using a threshold of $\lambda = 0.3$ in the objective function (see Equation (1)). This value has been established in the context of building footprints and has been shown to yield reliable results (Rutzinger, Rottensteiner, and Pfeifer 2009; Fan et al. 2014; Naumann, Bonerath, and Haunert 2025). However, previous studies found that not all geographic objects are equally complex to digitise (Coillie et al. 2014). We therefore also performed additional runs with varying λ to ensure the transferability of our experiments and discuss these results below.

5.1. Datasets

To enable a large-scale evaluation of automatically delineated field polygons for our first case study, we use the EU-wide dataset published by Batiç (2024), hereafter referred to as SAT, and compare it with official IACS data. Since the SAT polygons were derived from satellite imagery captured in 2022, it was necessary to obtain IACS data from the same year to ensure temporal consistency for meaningful comparisons. As no 2022 data is currently listed in the *EuroCrops* project (Schneider et al. 2023), we could not directly rely on its dataset. However, by following the referenced data sources provided by *EuroCrops*, we collected 2022 IACS data for five countries: Austria, Denmark, France, Netherlands, and Slovakia. An overview of the datasets used in this study is provided in Table 1.

Given that the SAT data is derived from satellite imagery, the delineated polygons represent homogeneous agricultural parcels, each typically corresponding to a single crop. To ensure compatibility, we selected the most detailed level of IACS data available (i.e. the GSAA data) containing annual, self-declared crop fields (see Section 3). In the following, we refer to such IACS data as GSAA.

As part of our second case study, we aim to assess the consistency between two commonly used reference data sources with respect to both their thematic and geometric characteristics. To this end, we match and compare IACS data with land use polygons from Germany’s official topographic database ATKIS.

Table 1. Number of polygons in the SAT and GSAA datasets for each country. All datasets refer to the year 2022.

Dataset	# Polygons	
	SAT	GSAA
Austria (AT)	692,019	2,600,000
Denmark (DK)	368,247	576,758
France (FR)	5,967,727	9,896,777
Netherlands (NL)	441,578	758,504
Slovakia (SK)	133,191	264,084

Specifically, we use IACS data maintained in the Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS), which represents higher-level agricultural land parcels classified into the three main land use classes *arable land*, *grassland*, and *permanent crops*. Ensuring a comparable level of thematic and geometric detail, we use the ATKIS Basis-DLM, the most detailed digital landscape model, which is derived from topographic maps at a scale of 1:25,000. We limit our experimental area to the federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia and we filter the ATKIS data to include only agricultural land use polygons matching the three classes of the LPIS data. While arable land and grassland are already represented as separate classes in ATKIS, polygons corresponding to permanent crops are distributed across more detailed subcategories. Following the official LPIS definition of permanent crops, we therefore group the relevant ATKIS subcategories (such as tree nurseries, vineyards, and fruit and nut plantations).

To further account for temporal consistency, we use LPIS data³ referring to the 2025 agricultural year and ATKIS data⁴ accessed on August 6, 2025. The LPIS dataset has 398,101 polygons, while the ATKIS dataset has 316,348 polygons. In the following, we refer to both datasets as LPIS and ATKIS, respectively.

5.2. Evaluation metrics

To evaluate our matching-based dataset comparisons, we conduct both spatial and thematic assessments. For the spatial comparisons, we apply different metrics which we briefly introduce in the following.

To obtain a general overview of how well two datasets align, we derive a score for each two matched datasets, as proposed by Naumann, Bonerath, and Haunert (2025). A matching M computed by the algorithm is associated with an objective value $\sigma(M)$ (see Equation (1)). Naturally, the optimal score would be achieved between two perfectly equal datasets $L_1 = L_2$. In this case, every polygon of one dataset is matched to exactly one polygon of the opposing dataset. Regarding the objective $\sigma(M)$, this means that every match has an IoU of 1, and $\sigma(M) = |L_1| \cdot (1 - \lambda)$. This value represents the optimal score. The objective value obtained from our actual matching can thus be compared to this optimum to assess overall performance. Accordingly, we define an *overall matching score*

$$s(M) = \frac{\sigma(M)}{\min\{|L_1|, |L_2|\} \cdot (1 - \lambda)} \cdot 100\% \quad (2)$$

as the proportion of the objective value achieved relative to the theoretical optimum. The use of $\min\{|L_1|, |L_2|\}$ accounts for differences in the number of polygons between the two datasets. Since a perfect one-to-one matching is only possible up to the size of the smaller dataset, this formulation ensures that the score is bounded by the best matching that is actually achievable with the concrete numbers of polygons per input dataset. In our context, we evaluate the quality of the smaller input dataset by comparing it against the larger reference dataset.

Since the overall matching score is highly influenced by unmatched polygons, it provides limited insight into the spatial alignment of corresponding field polygons between the two datasets. Thus, to enable the spatial assessment of the identified correspondences between two datasets (i.e. the matches), we introduce an IoU match quality

$$q_{\text{IoU}}(\mu) = \frac{\text{IoU}(\mu) - \lambda}{1 - \lambda} \cdot 100\% \quad (3)$$

for each match μ . With respect to the objective function in Equation (1), it indicates the proportion of the achieved matching quality relative to the theoretical optimum. Note that, since we set $\lambda = 0.3$, the optimal quality of a match is 0.7, which is why we normalise q_{IoU} by dividing by $1 - \lambda$ to make sure it lies in $[0, 1]$. The closer this score is to 1 the better the areas of the shapes align. It is exactly 1 if and only if the shapes are identical.

However, the evaluation of the matchings produced by our algorithm is not limited to the IoU as a geometric measure. Thus, as a complement to the IoU, we additionally consider an alternative geometric quality metric introduced by Möller et al. (2013). Their approach defines a score that combines the geometric mean of area ratios and the relative centroid distances between the polygons of a match

$\mu = \{P, Q\}$ and their pointwise intersection $I(\mu)$. In their original formulation, only pairs of single polygons p and q are compared, effectively resolving 1:n and m:n matches into their individual 1:1 relationships. Since our aim is to evaluate the quality of entire matches, we treat each set P and Q as a single dissolved multipolygon if it contains more than one polygon.

For each (multi-)polygon $P \in \mu$, we refer to $\bar{P} = P \setminus I(\mu)$ as the geometric difference and define $\gamma(P)$ as the centroid of P . Analogously to Möller et al. (2013), we introduce a relative offset

$$\Gamma_{\text{rel}}(I(\mu), P) = 1 - \frac{|\gamma(I(\mu)) - \gamma(P)|}{|\gamma(I(\mu)) - \gamma(\bar{P})|} \quad (4)$$

for each (multi-)polygon $P \in \mu$. If \bar{P} is a multipolygon composed of multiple disconnected single polygons, then $\gamma(\bar{P})$ refers to the centroid of the single polygon within \bar{P} that maximises the distance to the centroid of the intersection, i.e. $|\gamma(I(\mu)) - \gamma(\bar{P})|$. For the intersection $I(\mu)$ itself, we always consider the centre of mass as the centroid $\gamma(I(\mu))$, even if it is a multipolygon consisting of multiple disconnected polygons.

Using the definition of $\Gamma_{\text{rel}}(I(\mu), P)$, we introduce a *combined match quality*

$$q_{\text{comb}}(\mu) = \sqrt[4]{\frac{I(\mu)^2}{A(P) \cdot A(Q)} \cdot \Gamma_{\text{rel}}(I(\mu), P) \cdot \Gamma_{\text{rel}}(I(\mu), Q)} \quad (5)$$

with $A(P)$ being the area of a (multi-)polygon P .

The resulting score $q_{\text{comb}}(\mu)$ quantifies the ratio of the intersection area to the areas of the input polygons, which is conceptually similar to the IoU. However, in addition, it incorporates the relative offset between the centroids of the intersection, the input polygons, and the portions of the polygons that do not overlap with their matching counterparts. Finally, the geometric mean of all of those factors is taken. This way, matches need to have not only a high ratio of intersection area to the input polygon areas, but also a small relative offset (resulting in a high Γ_{rel} value close to 1) to be awarded a high score with respect to q_{comb} . For a more detailed description of the metric, we refer to the work of Möller et al. (2013).

5.3. Case study 1: SAT vs. GSAA

In our first case study, we conduct large-scale comparisons between the SAT and GSAA datasets listed in Table 1. Specifically, we evaluate the spatial alignment of both data sources at the level of the complete datasets as well as for individual matches. We apply two different geometric metrics, analyse visual examples, and examine how well the datasets align in terms of spatial consistency and granularity, i.e. by studying the distribution of matching multiplicities. In addition, we explore semantic aspects in more detail by analysing the matching quality across different thematic crop categories.

Overall Matching Quality. To evaluate the spatial alignment between the SAT and GSAA datasets, we first consider their overall matching scores (see Equation 2). The results are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Overall matching scores for the matchings between the SAT and GSAA datasets.

We observe that the scores are relatively low, with the best matchings (in Denmark and the Netherlands) reaching only about half of the maximum achievable score. The primary reason for this is the presence of unmatched polygons that occur when fields in the GSAA dataset do not have sufficient spatial overlap with those in the SAT dataset, or vice versa. Figure 6 highlights this by showing the distribution of polygons, categorised into matched polygons and unmatched polygons that occur exclusively in either SAT or GSAA.

Although for each country, correspondences could be found for the majority of polygons, a large number of polygons appear exclusively in the GSAA dataset. The share of such polygons ranges between 14% and 44% across the countries. A visual example of such a case is shown in Figure 7. While some polygons from both datasets overlap well, many fields present in the GSAA data are missing in the SAT dataset. Since the GSAA is based on official administrative records, this can be attributed to a deficiency in the SAT data, where actual agricultural fields were not correctly detected.

As a complement to the previously discussed case, only between 2% and 6% of all polygons are exclusively in the SAT dataset without corresponding entities in the GSAA data (see Figure 6). Visual examples of such cases are shown in Figure 8. Specifically, in Figure 8(a) and 8(b) we can observe detected fields that are actually green spaces within a golf course and clusters of panels in a solar park, respectively.

While these specific SAT polygons were misclassified, the general presence of SAT polygons without corresponding GSAA entities is not always due to classification errors. GSAA includes only those parcels

Figure 6. Distribution of all polygons in SAT and GSAA combined, categorised as matched polygons, polygons unique to SAT, and polygons unique to GSAA.

Figure 7. Excerpt from the Netherlands datasets showing most GSAA polygons (orange) having no corresponding SAT polygons (dashed blue outlines). Background imagery by Google (2025).

Figure 8. Examples of SAT polygons (dashed blue outlines) with no corresponding GSAAs (orange), taken from the datasets of the Netherlands. The scale shown in (a) applies to all subfigures. *Background imagery by Google (2025).*

Figure 9. Distribution of both the IoU-based and combined match qualities for the matches between SAT and GSAAs.

for which subsidies were requested under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) (see Section 3). As a result, some SAT polygons may correspond to actual crop fields that are simply not represented in the GSAAs. An example of this case is shown in Figure 8(c).

Overall, when interpreting unmatched polygons, we emphasise caution in attributing them solely to classification errors. It is important to keep in mind that perfect ground truth exists only in very rare cases. In our scenario, particularly with respect to unmatched SAT polygons, such discrepancies can have multiple causes: not only misclassification, but also differences in definitions, subsidy regulations, or temporal misalignment between datasets.

Spatial Match Qualities. Beyond assessing the overall matching quality that also includes unmatched polygons, we now focus specifically on the identified correspondences between SAT and GSAAs. To this end, we analyse both the IoU match qualities $q_{IoU}(\mu)$ (see Equation 3) and the combined match qualities $q_{comb}(\mu)$ (see Equation 5) shown in Figure 9. Both metrics range from 0 to 100, with 100 representing the optimal score.

For all countries and for both $q_{IoU}(\mu)$ and $q_{comb}(\mu)$, we observe that approximately 75 percent of all matches achieve more than half of the optimal quality score. In general, it is noticeable that the combined quality scores are systematically higher than the IoU-based scores, and they also exhibit a smaller spread toward lower values. This can be attributed to the fact that in the combined match quality, the congruence of polygon centroids has a strong influence on the score. As a result, the score is more permissive in cases

of over- and under-segmentation, where the SAT polygons are smaller or larger than the corresponding GSAA polygon, but their centroids still align well.

However, some country-specific patterns can be identified from both metrics. In particular, Denmark and the Netherlands show a notably smaller spread toward lower qualities compared to the other countries, indicating a consistently reasonable alignment of polygon correspondences. In contrast, Slovakia reveals diverging interpretations between the two metrics: while the IoU-based quality scores are relatively low and widely spread, the combined quality scores suggest a considerably better spatial alignment between the datasets.

While such plot-based evaluations provide a general overview of the distribution of matching qualities across the different countries, they fall short in capturing local patterns and regional systematics. To be able to identify such characteristics, we can use the interactive map viewer that we provide with this article (see Section 5.7). As an example, the heatmap in Figure 10 illustrates the local spatial alignment between SAT and GSAA data for Austria. Specifically, it shows the IoU-based match quality where unmatched polygons are treated as matched with a quality of 0. Visualising the match qualities in their geographic context reveals a clear spatial pattern: the high number of unmatched polygons (see Figure 6) and the low match qualities (see Figure 9) are primarily concentrated in mountainous regions. In contrast, areas with flatter topography have reasonably high match qualities. We attribute this pattern to the steep and complex terrain in alpine regions that makes it difficult to extract distinct field boundaries from satellite imagery. In these areas, the GSAA dataset contains a large number of polygons classified as alpine pasture (*‘Almfutterfläche’*), which represent extensive and diffuse land parcels that are difficult to delineate. As a result, these polygons are often not represented in the automatically delineated SAT data.

Distribution of Multiplicities. To further evaluate the consistency in terms of spatial granularity across the SAT and GSAA datasets, we analyse the distribution of all matched polygons according to their match multiplicities: one-to-one (1:1), one-to-many (1: n), and many-to-many ($m:n$). Figure 11 presents this decomposition for each country under investigation.

Across all countries, a higher proportion of SAT polygons is involved in 1:1 matches compared to GSAA polygons. This indicates a higher spatial granularity in the GSAA dataset, where multiple GSAA polygons often correspond to a single SAT polygon. Consequently, a larger share of GSAA polygons participate in 1: n matches than SAT polygons. A visual example of such a case is shown in the top-left of Figure 8(b). While the majority of these cases involve low multiplicities (e.g. 1:2 or 1:3 matches), extreme instances also occur. An example of such a match with a multiplicity of 1:179 is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 10. Heatmap of the IoU-based match quality q_{IoU} from the perspective of all polygons included in the GSAA dataset of Austria. The background is taken from OpenTopoMap (OSM 2025).

Figure 11. Distribution of all matched polygons in the GSAA (left bars) and SAT (right bars) datasets according to their allocation as 1:1, 1:n, and m:n matches.

Figure 12. A 1:179 match between one SAT polygon (dashed blue outline) and 179 GSAA polygons (orange). *Background imagery by Google (2025).*

Overall, many-to-many relationships are rare, suggesting that overlapping polygons from both datasets generally align well spatially and differ primarily in their level of granularity. Most many-to-many matches involve moderate complexities, such as 2:3 or 3:2 relationships.

Crop-Specific Match Assessment. While the previous assessments provide an overview of matching characteristics across the countries, they do not differentiate between the thematic crop classes. However, analysing the matches by crop type offers deeper insights into whether certain classes are more prone to mismatches or geometric incongruencies in the SAT data.

While the SAT polygons do not provide thematic information, the GSAA data contains detailed crop type information for each field. Using the Netherlands as an example, we therefore examine the match quality of the GSAA polygons, grouped by crop type. Since the thematic classification in the Dutch GSAA dataset is very detailed and comprises more than 300 crop types, we have grouped them semantically according to our own considerations. These broader categories include *cereals*, *flowers & bulbs*, *grasslands*, *roots & tubers*, and *others*.

Figure 13 shows the corresponding IoU-based match qualities (see Equation 3). The results show that fields classified as cereals and roots & tubers align spatially well across the GSAA and SAT data. In contrast, particularly the category flowers & bulbs has a wide spread in match quality, with a notable number of polygons in lower-quality matches.

Figure 13. IoU-based match qualities per crop category for the matches between SAT and GSAA in the Netherlands. From left to right, the icons represent *cereals*, *flowers & bulbs*, *grasslands*, *roots & tubers*, and *others*.

Figure 14. Distribution of GSAA polygons in the Netherlands by match multiplicity (unmatched, 1:1, 1:n, m:n), split by crop category. From left to right, the icons represent *cereals*, *flowers & bulbs*, *grasslands*, *roots & tubers*, and *others*.

To further investigate these patterns, Figure 14 shows the distribution of GSAA polygons by match multiplicity, also including unmatched cases. The data shows that cereals and roots & tubers have both a substantially lower proportion of unmatched polygons as well as a higher proportion of 1:1 matches compared to the other classes. This observation is consistent with the high spatial match qualities within these two classes.

Taken together, these findings suggest that fields of cereals and roots & tubers can be reliably delineated from satellite imagery using automated methods (such as those used for SAT). In contrast, other thematic classes tend to have greater discrepancies in geometric shape and a higher proportion of entirely undetected fields.

5.4. Case study 2: ATKIS vs. LPIS

In our second case study, we investigate how well the two established reference datasets ATKIS and LPIS align both thematically and geometrically. To identify potential semantic discrepancies, we analyse the three land use classes (arable land, grassland, and permanent crops) separately.

Semantic Consistency. First, we assess the semantic consistency between the two datasets by analysing, for each polygon, the land use class of its matched polygon(s) in the other dataset. In the case of 1:1 correspondences, this is straightforward, as each polygon is matched to exactly one polygon of a specific class. For 1:n and m:n relationships, we determine, for each polygon, the proportion of corresponding entities of each class within the match. Figure 15 shows the resulting distribution of polygons with respect

Figure 15. Distribution of LPIS and ATKIS polygons by the land use classes of their matched polygon(s) in the respective other dataset. For 1:1 correspondences, each polygon is matched to a single class; for 1:n and m:n relationships, class proportions are used. Unmatched polygons are shown separately in grey.

Figure 16. A breakdown of the unmatched ATKIS polygons of type permanent crop (> 50% of the rightmost bar in Figure 15) by subcategory. For readability reasons, only categories with at least 5 occurrences are shown.

to the thematic classes they are matched to, as well as the share of unmatched polygons (i.e. polygons with no identified correspondences).

We observe that for arable land only a small fraction of polygons remain unmatched, and the vast majority of matches are thematically consistent. This suggests a high degree of alignment between the datasets, both spatially and semantically. For grassland, over 60 percent of polygons in both datasets are still matched with thematic consistency. However, compared to arable land, the proportion of unmatched polygons is noticeably higher, indicating a lower overall spatial congruence.

This observation becomes even more pronounced for permanent crops. Less than 30 percent of polygons in both datasets are matched with thematic consistency. Furthermore, the share of unmatched polygons is notably higher in ATKIS than in LPIS, reaching more than 50 percent. A possible explanation for this discrepancy is that LPIS includes only agriculturally used areas that are relevant for EU agricultural subsidies. Certain types of permanent crops represented in ATKIS may be absent from LPIS if they are not eligible for funding. To support this assumption, Figure 16 shows the distribution of unmatched ATKIS polygons of type permanent crop into their individual subcategories. It can be seen that polygons of type *tree nursery* account for over 90 percent of the unmatched polygons. Hence, it is likely that tree nurseries do not fall under the category of agricultural land eligible for EU funding, and are therefore absent from the LPIS data.

Another notable observation is that approximately 50 percent of all permanent crops in the LPIS data are thematically inconsistently matched to polygons classified as arable land in the ATKIS data. One possible explanation for this inconsistency might be overlaps between the definitions of permanent crops in LPIS and arable land in ATKIS. According to the AdV (2022), arable land in ATKIS is defined as ‘*area for growing field crops (e.g. cereals, legumes, root crops) and berries (e.g. strawberries)*’. In contrast, permanent crops in LPIS are defined as ‘*non-rotational crops other than permanent grassland and*

permanent pasture that occupy the land for five years or more and that yield repeated harvests, including nurseries and short rotation coppice' (European Parliament and Council of the European Union 2021). From these definitions, one could speculate that certain types of berries (which occupy a field for more than five years) might be classified as permanent crop in LPIS and as arable land in ATKIS. However, since both LPIS and ATKIS do not provide information on the specific crop type, a precise determination of the causes of these mismatches remains challenging.

Spatial Congruency. Beyond considering the semantic consistency of ATKIS and LPIS, we further focus on the spatial congruency of the matched polygons. To this end, we analyse the distribution of the IoU-based match qualities (see Equation 3), split into the three land use classes arable land, grassland, and permanent crops. Since it is not always possible to unambiguously assign a match to a single class when it involves multiple polygons of different classes, we evaluate the match quality from the perspective of each individual polygon. That is, for each polygon, we assess the quality of the match in which it is involved. Figure 17 shows this distribution of quality scores from both the LPIS and the ATKIS perspectives.

In comparison to the match qualities between SAT and GSAA (see Figures 9 and 13), we generally observe higher match qualities across all thematic classes. This is not surprising, as we are comparing agricultural land use data from two official sources. However, differences between the three land use classes are still evident. Most notably, the match quality for arable land is very high, with only minor variation. This suggests that arable land parcels are represented consistently across ATKIS and LPIS, not only thematically (see Figure 15), but also spatially. In contrast, the match quality is noticeably lower for grassland. Although 75 percent of the polygons still are part of matches achieving more than 60 percent of the optimal quality, the spread extends further toward lower values. For permanent crops, we also observe differences between the polygons in ATKIS and LPIS. Polygons modelled as permanent crops in ATKIS are assigned to matches with lower quality compared to those in LPIS. A possible reason for this could be differences in the classification criteria.

Importance of Temporal Alignment. Although we used the most recent available version of the ATKIS dataset, AdV (2022) state that the data is comprehensively updated on a three-year cycle. While the available metadata provide timestamps for each ATKIS polygon, these only indicate the start of its validity. It is not clear if, or when, semantic or geometric updates were made. Therefore, it is also possible that the ATKIS data is not temporally aligned with LPIS. Such a temporal misalignment can affect both the semantic consistency and spatial congruency of the two datasets. For example, the high proportion of permanent crops in LPIS that are thematically mismatched to arable land in ATKIS (see Figure 15) could also be explained by this issue. Fields labelled as arable land in ATKIS may have since been converted to permanent crops, changes that are already captured in the more up-to-date LPIS dataset.

In addition to semantic inconsistencies, temporal misalignment between the datasets can also lead to discrepancies in the geometric congruency of fields. If field geometries change from one year to the next but only one dataset is updated accordingly, this inevitably reduces the spatial match quality. Depending

Figure 17. IoU-based match quality per land use class. For each polygon of the LPIS and ATKIS data, the quality of its corresponding match is assessed.

on the extent of the geometric changes, our algorithm may not be able to recognise a correspondence between two fields that actually belong together. In such extreme cases, this would impair the intended applications of our approach, such as data fusion and enrichment.

However, with respect to our case study, we emphasise that we gathered the datasets in a way that ensures the best possible temporal alignment. Still, missing (or poorly documented) metadata made it difficult to fully rule out temporal discrepancies.

Overall, our analysis shows that, although both ATKIS and LPIS are established sources of reference data, notable spatial and thematic inconsistencies can be observed between them. In line with the findings of Foody (2024), this highlights the importance of not naively assuming the perfection of any dataset used as ground truth. Instead, reference data should be carefully evaluated in advance to determine its application-specific suitability (e.g. for validating model outputs).

5.5. Runtime and memory analysis

We tracked both the running times and the maximum memory usage for the executions per dataset comparison. The corresponding results are shown in Figures 18 and 19, respectively. In addition to the country-level datasets listed in Table 1, the abbreviation NW refers to the comparison of ATKIS and LPIS datasets for North Rhine-Westphalia.

Figure 18. Running times of the matching algorithm applied with 64 threads. In blue, the total execution time is plotted in seconds. In yellow, we show the average execution time per connected component of the input datasets in milliseconds.

Figure 19. The peak memory used by the matching with 64 threads per dataset in GB.

We observe that the matching for France requires the longest running time and the highest memory, which is directly correlated to the data size, i.e. the number of polygons in both datasets. The peak memory usages are caused by the final output computations, which involve loading the entire datasets into memory to label the polygons with matching information.

To be able to analyse the running times relative to the number of input polygons, we additionally plot the average time required to process each (connected) component per dataset (see Figure 18). This is an indication of how hard the components were to solve and is not distorted by the total number of input polygons anymore. Here we see that the Slovakia dataset has the highest average running time per component, being ≈ 0.4 ms. This implies that Slovakia has many non-trivial components. As shown in Figure 8, many components are trivial to solve, as they only contain one polygon that cannot be matched because it does not intersect any polygon of the opposing dataset. Similarly, components consisting of two polygons (one per dataset) are straightforward to solve as no hierarchy has to be built.

Overall, we observe that the algorithm is well-suited for the use case of agricultural land use polygons. As previously demonstrated for building footprints by Naumann, Bonerath, and Haunert (2025), the approach also exhibits linear scalability in this context, despite the generally higher geometric complexity of field polygons. The running time mostly depends on the complexity of the components to be solved. Regardless of the total number of input polygons, the average time for solving a single component remained below a millisecond. Even for the largest dataset, memory consumption stayed below 40 GB, indicating that the algorithm can be applied on today's standard computing systems.

5.6. On the choice of λ

As stated at the beginning of this section, we used $\lambda = 0.3$ for all of the experiments discussed above. To ensure the robustness of our results concerning changes of this parameter, we additionally computed the matchings with choices of λ in 0.0, 0.1, ..., 0.5. The running time variance between the runs for $\lambda = 0.1, \dots, 0.5$ was negligible. Only for $\lambda = 0.0$, we measured running times that were up to a factor of ≈ 2 times those of the larger λ values. This was to be expected, since many of the reduction techniques proposed by Naumann, Bonerath, and Haunert (2024) cannot be applied here. However, we argue that even with twice the running time, the algorithm is applicable to large datasets in a scalable manner.

It remains to explore the robustness of the matching results when varying λ . To this end, we measured the distributions of the fractions of polygons in the respective match multiplicities, see Figure 20. The analysis shows that the general structure of the computed optimal matchings does not change when varying λ . Rather, we see small differences in the matching compositions: When increasing λ , we observe an increasing number of unmatched polygons. At the same time, the share of polygons in $m:n$ matches increases at the cost of decreasing shares in 1:1 and 1:n matches. This is intended behaviour due to the nature of the datasets: Often, the datasets agree on the outer boundaries of an agricultural area, but differ in their subdivision. In these cases, with increasing λ , it gets impossible to form 1:1 and 1:n matches that

Figure 20. The fraction of input polygons in every match multiplicity over all datasets and variations of λ in percent.

exceed an IoU of λ and the optimal solution has to revert to a bigger $m:n$ match of the entire area. This emphasises the usage potential of λ as a granularity control. Hence, we demonstrate that, although varying λ within a reasonable range does influence the outcome in a controlled manner, it does not substantially alter the matching results. This suggests that our findings are robust and can be transferred to other parameter choices that may be better suited for a specific use case or data basis.

5.7. Interactive map viewer

While quantitatively evaluating the identified spatial correspondences of the matching algorithm allows for general statements about the completeness and consistency of two datasets, it does not provide an intuitive overview of their agreement in the geographical context. For this reason, we developed a web-based visualisation tool that displays different comparison metrics within an interactive map viewer. To give a look and feel of our tool, we provide a directly executable demo that visualises the case studies presented in this article (see [Section 1](#) for the web link).

Our HTML-based tool enables the visualisation of the matching algorithm results for different dataset comparisons. For an analysis of the spatial alignment, the metrics used in our evaluations can be visualised, i.e. the IoU-based match quality and the combined match quality. To further illustrate granularity differences between two datasets, the distribution of match multiplicities can be displayed. For each dataset, the visualisation indicates the number of polygons in the other dataset that each polygon is matched with. Whenever the two compared datasets include thematic attributes that allow for an assessment of semantic consistency, our tool also provides a corresponding visualisation.

In addition to these metrics, different map backgrounds can be selected, and the displayed colour scale can be dynamically adjusted according to the desired sensitivity. This helps to better identify correlations between data characteristics and geographical features.

To address the aspect of reproducibility, we not only provide a demo showcasing the case study results but also share the full implementation of our web-based tool. To close the workflow from executing the provided matching algorithm code to using the interactive tool, we additionally include a GUI-based interface that allows users to convert the matching outputs into .csv files directly readable by the visualisation tool.

6. Conclusion and future work

In this work, we adapted an efficient matching algorithm to enable large-scale comparisons of agricultural field polygons. This facilitates not only systematic quality assessments of model outputs but also supports the integration of complementary data sources by data fusion.

Our experimental evaluation emphasised the potential of the method as a tool for supporting both quality assurance and harmonisation efforts.

Beyond its standalone application, our approach could be integrated into a unified research data infrastructure as part of a shared data quality assessment framework, where it serves as a component for evaluating and harmonising agricultural land use data from different sources.

To facilitate the practical use of the approach, we provide an open-source implementation of the matching algorithm. Additionally, we share a web-based visualisation tool that allows users to intuitively explore and compare two datasets with respect to their spatial and thematic alignment in a geographically contextualised manner.

Beyond its practical utility, we showed the high performance of the approach. Despite instance sizes of up to 10 million polygons, the algorithm identified spatial matches within just a few minutes, highlighting its scalability for large-scale applications.

While our study has demonstrated the general suitability of the proposed matching algorithm for agricultural applications, it also opens up several promising directions for future research. One direction lies in applying the approach to more diverse comparison scenarios within agricultural sciences, including in-depth investigations of how the spatial match quality correlates with contextual factors such as

topography or geometric complexity. These insights could help identify systematic challenges in specific landscape types or farming practices.

Furthermore, our matching approach offers potential for advancing data enrichment and harmonisation efforts. This could be realised by using the correspondences to guide state-of-the-art machine learning models in inferring missing or inconsistent semantic attributes, improving interoperability and enabling more comprehensive data fusion. Additionally, the correspondences computed by our method can be utilised to improve existing machine learning approaches for agricultural field delineation by providing an automated single-entity level quality determination in regions where a ground truth exists.

From an empirical perspective, we evaluated our approach using the IoU as the core metric within our matching optimisation. While this measure is well-established in the literature and performed reliably in our work, it may still fail to capture narrow and elongated fields, as often found in smallholder farming systems, especially when datasets are of lower quality or contain distortions and offsets. Such cases should be explored in future work by tailoring the objective function to put more emphasis on shape similarities and no longer strictly requiring a high intersection ratio. This can be easily integrated into our framework by adjusting the weights assigned to the edges in the matching procedure and relaxing the connectivity constraint to a minimum-distance constraint, thereby maintaining efficiency and scalability through parallelisation. Alternatively, in cases of large-scale distortions, one could add an alignment as a pre-processing step, either on local zones or entire datasets, to enable IoU-based matching in these cases as well and explore the method's effectiveness.

Endnotes

1. <https://www2.geoinfo.uni-bonn.de/html/visualization/MatchVis/map.html>
2. <https://github.com/anaumannig/LandUsePolyMatching>
3. https://www.opengeodata.nrw.de/produkte/umwelt_klima/bodennutzung/landwirtschaft/
4. <https://www.opengeodata.nrw.de/produkte/geobasis/lm/akt/basis-dlm/>

Author contributions

CRediT: **Alexander Naumann**: Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing; **Sven Gedicke**: Data curation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing; **Jan-Henrik Haurert**: Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Disclosure statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available: EU field boundaries at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14229033>, Eurocrops at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6868143>, LPIS at https://www.opengeodata.nrw.de/produkte/umwelt_klima/bodennutzung/landwirtschaft/ and ATKIS at <https://www.opengeodata.nrw.de/produkte/geobasis/lm/akt/basis-dlm/>

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